

**Ko‘p o‘zgaruvchili funksiyalarning hususiy hosilalari va
differensiallashlar haqida**

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Annotatsiya.

Ushbu maqolada ayrim masalalarning hususiy hosilalari va differensiallarini yechilish usullari keltirilgan.

Аннотация

В статье представлены методы решения специальных производных и дифференциалов некоторых задач.

Annotation

The article presents methods for solving special derivatives and differentials of some problems

Kalit so‘zlar. Xususiy hosila, differensiallanuvchi funksiya

$f(x) = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$ funksiya ochiq $M (M \subset R^m)$ to‘plamda berilgan bo‘lsin. Bu to‘plamda $x^0 = (x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$ nuqta olib, uning birinchi koordinatasi x_1^0 ga shunday $\Delta x_1 (\Delta x_1 > 0, \Delta x_1 < 0)$ ortirma beraylikki, $(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) \in M$ bo‘lsin. Natijada $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$ funksiya ham $(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$ nuqtada x_1 o‘zgaruvchisi bo‘yicha

$$\Delta_{x_1} f = f(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$$

xususiy orttirmaga ega bo‘ladi.

Ushbu

$$\frac{\Delta_{x_1} f}{\Delta x_1} = \frac{f(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{\Delta x_1} \quad (1.1)$$

nisbatni qaraylik. Ravshanki, bu nisbat Δx_1 ning funksiyasi bo‘lib, u Δx_1 ning noldan farqli qiymatlarida aniqlangan.

1.1 - ta’rif. Agar $\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0$ da (1.1) nisbatning limiti

$$\lim_{\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta_{x_1} f}{\Delta x_1} = \lim_{\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{\Delta x_1}$$

mavjud va chekli bo‘lsa, bu limit $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$ funksiyaning $(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$ nuqtadagi x_1 o‘zgaruvchisi bo‘yicha xususiy hosilasi deb ataladi va

$$\frac{\partial f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1}, f'_{x_1}(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0), f'_{x_1}$$

belgilarning biri bilan belgilanadi. Demak,

$$f'_{x_1}(x^0) = \frac{\partial f(x^0)}{\partial x_1} = \lim_{\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta_{x_1} f}{\Delta x_1}.$$

Agar $x_1^0 + \Delta x_1 = x_1$ deb olsak, unda $\Delta x_1 = x_1 - x_1^0$ va $\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0$ da $x_1 \rightarrow x_1^0$ bo‘lib, natijada

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta_{x_1} f}{\Delta x_1} &= \lim_{\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{\Delta x_1} = \\ &= \lim_{x_1 \rightarrow x_1^0} \frac{f(x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{x_1 - x_1^0} \end{aligned}$$

bo‘ladi. Demak, $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$ funksiyaning $(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$ nuqtadagi x_1 o‘zgaruvchisi bo‘yicha xususiy hosilasini ushbu

$$\frac{f(x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{x_1 - x_1^0}$$

nisbatning $x_1 \rightarrow x_1^0$ dagi limiti sifatida ta’riflash mumkin.

Xuddi shunga o‘xshash $f(x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$ funksiyaning boshqa o‘zgaruvchilari bo‘yicha xususiy hosilalari ta’riflanadi:

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2} = \lim_{\Delta x_2 \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1^0, x_2^0 + \Delta x_2, x_3^0, \dots, x_m^0) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{\Delta x_2}$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_m} = \lim_{\Delta x_m \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_{m-1}^0, x_m^0 + \Delta x_m) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)}{\Delta x_m}$$

Demak, ko‘p o‘zgaruvchili $f(x_1, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$ funksiyaning biror $(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$ nuqtada $x_k = (k = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ o‘zgaruvchisi bo‘yicha xususiy hosilasini ta’riflashda bu funksiyaning $x_k = (k = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ o‘zgaruvchidan boshqa barcha o‘zgaruvchilari o‘zgarmas deb hisoblanar ekan. Shunday qilib, $x_k = (k = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ funksiyaning xususiy hosilalari $f'_{x_1}, f'_{x_2}, \dots, f'_{x_m}$ bir o‘zgaruvchili funksiya hosilasi kabi ekanligini ko‘ramiz. Demak, ko‘p o‘zgaruvchili funksiyalarning xususiy hosilalarini hisoblashda bir o‘zgaruvchili funksiyaning hosilasini hisoblashdagi ma’lum bo‘lgan qoida va jadvallardan to‘liq foydalanish mumkin.

Misollar. 1. $f(x_1, x_2) = \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2}$ bo‘lsin. Bu funksiyaning $\forall (x_1, x_2) \in R^2$ nuqtadagi xususiy hosilalari

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1} = \frac{x_1}{\sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2}}, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2} = \frac{x_2}{\sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2}}$$

bo‘ladi.

$$2. f(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x_2}} e^{-\frac{x_1+x_2}{2}} \text{ funksiyaning } \forall (x_1, x_2) \in R^2 (x_2 > 0) \text{ nuqtadagi xususiy}$$

hosilalarini hisoblaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x_2}} e^{-\frac{x_1+x_2}{2}} \right) = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x_2}} e^{-\frac{x_1+x_2}{2}}, \\ \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x_2}} e^{-\frac{x_1+x_2}{2}} \right) = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x_2^3}} e^{-\frac{x_1+x_2}{2}} - \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x_2}} e^{-\frac{x_1+x_2}{2}} = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x_2}} e^{-\frac{x_1+x_2}{2}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{x_2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

3. Ushbu

$$f(x_1, x_2) = \begin{cases} \frac{2x_1x_2}{x_1^2 + x_2^2}, & \text{agar } (x_1, x_2) \neq (0, 0) \text{ bo'lsa,} \\ 0, & \text{agar } (x_1, x_2) = (0, 0) \text{ bo'lsa} \end{cases}$$

funksiyaning xususiy hosilalarini toping.

Aytaylik, $(x_1, x_2) \neq (0, 0)$ bo‘lsin. U holda

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{2x_1x_2}{x_1^2 + x_2^2} \right) = \frac{2x_2(x_1^2 + x_2^2) - 2x_1x_2 \cdot 2x_1}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2)^2} = \frac{2x_2(x_2^2 - x_1^2)}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2)^2}, \\ \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{2x_1x_2}{x_1^2 + x_2^2} \right) = \frac{2x_1(x_1^2 + x_2^2) - 2x_1x_2 \cdot 2x_2}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2)^2} = \frac{2x_1(x_1^2 - x_2^2)}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2)^2} \end{aligned}$$

bo‘ladi.

Endi $(x_1, x_2) = (0, 0)$ bo‘lsin. U holda

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f(0, 0)}{\partial x_1} &= \lim_{\Delta x_1 \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(\Delta x_1, 0) - f(0, 0)}{\Delta x_1} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial f(0, 0)}{\partial x_2} &= \lim_{\Delta x_2 \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(0, \Delta x_2) - f(0, 0)}{\Delta x_2} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

bo‘ladi.

Demak, berilgan $f(x_1, x_2)$ funksiya $\forall (x_1, x_2) \in R^2$ da xususiy hosilalarga ega.

Funksiyaning differensiallanuvchiligi tushunchasi.

$f(x) = f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$ funksiya ochiq $M (M \subset R^2)$ to‘plamda berilgan bo‘lsin.

Bu to‘plamda $(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0) = x^0$ nuqta bilan birga $(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1, x_2^0 + \Delta x_2, \dots, x_m^0 + \Delta x_m)$ nuqtani olib, berilgan funksiyaning to‘la orttirmasi

$$\Delta f(x^0) = f(x_1^0 + \Delta x_1, x_2^0 + \Delta x_2, \dots, x_m^0 + \Delta x_m) - f(x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_m^0)$$

ni qaraymiz.

Ravshanki, funksiyaning $\Delta f(x^0)$ orttirmasi argumentlar orttirmalari $\Delta x_1, \Delta x_2, \dots, \Delta x_m$ larga bog‘lik, bo‘lib, ko‘pchilik hollarda $\Delta x_1, \Delta x_2, \dots, \Delta x_m$ lar bilan Δf orasidagi bog‘lanish murakkab bo‘ladi. Tabiiyki, bunda $\Delta x_1, \Delta x_2, \dots, \Delta x_m$ larga ko‘ra Δf ni aniq yoki taqribiy hisoblash qiyinlashadi. Natijada orttirmasi $\Delta x_1, \Delta x_2, \dots, \Delta x_m$ orttirmalar bilan soddarog‘ bog‘lanishda bo‘lgan funksiyalarni o‘rganish masalasi yuzaga keladi.

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